

Studies on Sorption of Cadmium on some Soils of India

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Adsorption of cadmium has been studied on eight agricultural soils having pH range 6.0–9.2 and total cadmium content 0.45–0.95 $\mu\text{g Cd g}^{-1}$ soil. The equilibrium was attained within 3 h. The adsorption isotherms followed the Freundlich adsorption equation and isotherms were of 'L' type as defined by Giles *et al.* Desorption was also studied on three soils with variable pH; with the soil of lowest pH (soil no. 1; equilibrium pH 5.6), Cd desorbed by repeated washings with 0.002 M CaCl_2 , was >85% while in soils 8 and 4 with equilibrium pH values 6.4 and 7.9 it was only 49 and 30%, respectively. The amount of Cd desorbed from the three soils by 125 or 500 $\mu\text{m ml}^{-1}$ solution of heavy metal chlorides varied from 3% to 85%. The results indicate that Cd is strongly sorbed by soils of high pH (>7.0) when it is added in amounts comparable to additions as sewage.

CADMIUM is one of the most difficult elements to remove from sewage sludge as it is more soluble in water and exists in divalent cationic form in soil, therefore, it is easily available to plants¹.

The purpose of this experiment was to study adsorption of Cd on eight soils, in the trace amounts of Cd (175 $\mu\text{g Cd g}^{-1}$ soil and 0–80 $\mu\text{g Cd ml}^{-1}$ solute) that could occur with applications of sewage sludges and/or phosphatic fertilisers. The desorption of Cd from soils by other divalent cations was also studied.

Experimental

Eight top soil samples (0–20 cm), with no previous history of cadmium addition, from different parts of India were collected. These soils had wide range of properties (Table 1). The mechanical composition of the soil was determined by international pipette method, while that of pH in 0.01 M CaCl_2 solution (1:2.5), CaCO_3 , organic matter, free Fe_2O_3 and cation-exchange capacity (CEC) by standard techniques². The mineralogical composition of the clay fraction was studied by X-ray diffractions. The specific surface area was determined by ethylene glycol monoethyl ether method³. Total cadmium was determined by treating the soil with HF and HClO_4 as described by Jackson for copper. Extractable cadmium was determined by shaking the samples (2 g) of soils for 4 h with 25 ml of 0.002 M CaCl_2 , 0.05 M CaCl_2 , 0.5 M acetic acid and 0.05 M EDTA neutralised to pH 7 with ammonia. The suspensions were filtered and its Cd content was determined by an atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Adsorption experiments were performed by shaking the soil sample (2 g) with CdCl_2 (0–25 ml; 125 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) prepared in 0.002 M CaCl_2 in glass stoppered tubes for 4 h. The volume of each tube

was adjusted to 25 ml with distilled water (equilibrium pH range 5.6–7.9). The effect of time on adsorption was studied on three soils (sample nos. 1, 4, 8) by shaking the soil sample (2 g) for 0.5–36 h with CdCl_2 (25 ml; concn. as above). The suspensions were filtered at different time intervals and aliquots of the filtrate taken for determination of Cd. The amount of Cd adsorbed were calculated as the decrease in its amount in solution.

Cumulative desorption experiments with CaCl_2 were conducted to study the amount of Cd which can be desorbed by repeated washings with CaCl_2 , on three soils (sample nos. 1, 4, 8) by shaking the soil samples (10 g) with CdCl_2 solution (100 ml; 125 $\mu\text{m ml}^{-1}$) containing 0.002 M CaCl_2 for 4 h. The suspensions were centrifuged and 50 ml of the supernatant was withdrawn, and the amount of Cd sorbed was determined as the decrease in its concentration in solution. Then 0.002 M CaCl_2 (50 ml) was added to the remaining suspension, shaken for 4 h, centrifuged as above, and 50 ml of the supernatant was withdrawn. The treatment was repeated 9 times giving a total of 10 successive aliquots of 50 ml supernatant withdrawn. Aliquots were taken from each of the supernatant solution for the determination of Cd.

Desorption experiments were made on Cd adsorbed soil samples (as described above) by shaking soil samples with 25 ml. of water, CaCl_2 , CuCl_2 , PbCl_2 and ZnCl_2 of 125 $\mu\text{m ml}^{-1}$ or 500 $\mu\text{m ml}^{-1}$ for 4 h. The suspensions were centrifuged and Cd in supernatant was determined as above.

All the experiments were conducted in duplicate.

Results and Discussion

The amount of total Cd present in all the soils was the same as in uncontaminated soil^{4,5} (0.45–0.94 $\mu\text{g Cd g}^{-1}$ soil). Extraction of the soil by

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SOILS

Sample no.	Place	Soil type	Silt %	Clay (>2 μm) %	pH (1:2.5)	Organic C %	CaCO ₃ %	Free Fe ₂ O ₃ %	OEC meq/100 g	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹	Major clay mineral
1	Banglore	Red	48.1	18.3	6.0	0.44	0.6	10.2	6.5	21.2	Kaolinite, quartz
2	Datawali	Saline calcareous	37.5	9.0	7.2	0.40	5.2	8.6	10.0	24.3	Illite, quartz, calcite
3	Sikandra Rao	Alkaline sodic	52.5	4.0	9.2	0.35	8.2	6.8	10.4	36.6	Illite, quartz, chlorite
4	Hathras	Alluvial	38.8	19.1	7.9	0.56	8.0	3.6	11.6	30.9	Illite, quartz, calcite (traces)
5	Bank of Yamuna Tappal	Alkaline calcareous	27.1	8.5	8.1	0.54	9.0	6.7	8.0	26.4	Illite, quartz, calcite (traces)
6	Atrauli	Alkaline calcareous	22.6	4.4	8.5	0.44	10.8	5.4	9.4	34.8	Illite, quartz, chlorite, feldspar (traces)
7	Khair	Saline calcareous	44.9	15.2	7.5	0.50	6.6	5.6	9.6	27.2	Illite, quartz
8	Indore	Black	47.0	44.8	7.0	0.88	2.5	1.4	31.5	80.6	Illite, montmorillonite, quartz

CaCl₂, EDTA or acetic acid gave a very small amount of Cd present in the soil (Table 2). The equilibrium time for the adsorption of Cd on soil was taken as 4 h for the adsorption increased upto 3 h and thereafter it became nearly constant.

TABLE 2—TOTAL AND EXTRACTABLE Cd CONTENT OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SOILS

Sample no	Total Cd (μg Cd per g soil)	Extractable Cd (μg Cd per g soil)			
		CaCl ₂ 0.002 M	CaCl ₂ 0.05 M	Acetic acid 0.5 M	EDTA 0.05 M
1	0.643	0.009	0.059	0.032	0.056
2	0.514	0.010	0.062	0.066	0.034
3	0.449	0.007	0.034	0.098	0.068
4	0.572	0.004	0.019	0.047	0.096
5	0.614	0.010	0.042	0.066	0.104
6	0.538	0.008	0.049	0.077	0.132
7	0.702	0.006	0.053	0.051	0.156
8	0.944	0.016	0.077	0.115	0.226

The adsorption behaviour of Cd on all the soil samples can be described by the Freundlich adsorption equation. The values of 1/n were in the range 0.72–0.92 indicating 'L' type of adsorption isotherm as verified from Fig. 1. The values of Freundlich constant K (which indicates the extent of adsorption) were maximum for sample no. 8 and minimum for sample no. 1, indicating that maximum adsorption of Cd occurs with the former and minimum with the latter. The adsorption of Cd on soils was found in the order 8>4>5>7>6>2>3>1 (numerals indicate sample no.).

Fig. 1 indicates that adsorption isotherms were of 'L' type as defined by Giles *et al.*⁶, which may be due to the fact that vacant sites become less accessible with the progressive covering of adsorption surface. The initial nature of the isotherm indicates that Cd met no strong competition for adsorption sites from water. Adsorption capacity, cation-exchange capacity and organic water content

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of Cd adsorption on soil samples : (●) 1, (x) 4, and (○) 8.

were positively correlated. It may be due to the fact that organic matter is known to contribute 25–90% of total cation-exchange capacity of soil⁷. The order of Cd adsorption on different soils may be accounted by the different contents of free Fe₂O₃⁸, organic matter⁹, clay¹⁰, CaCO₃, pH¹¹ etc. The order of Cd adsorption on different soils is according to their cation-exchange capacity, organic matter and nature of clay minerals.

To study the relationship between retention capacity and specific area of soils, the distribution coefficient of Cd (K_d) and the surface density of the retained Cd (Γ) were calculated by the expressions,

$$K_d = \left(\frac{x/m}{C}\right); \quad \Gamma = \frac{x/m \cdot N \cdot 10^{-6}}{112.4 \cdot S}$$

where, (x/m) is the concentration of Cd retained in solid phase ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), C the equilibrium concentration in solution ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), N the Avogadro number, and S the specific area of the soil ($\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$). Fig. 2 reveals that the behaviour of the soils were similar and as with the increase in adsorption density K_d decreases showing a decrease in the affinity of the surface towards Cd; the affinity follow the order, $8 > 4 > 1$ (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TIME ON Cd ADSORPTION ON SOILS FROM $125 \mu\text{M ml}^{-1}$ Cd CONTAINING 0.002 M CaCl_2

Sample no	Time (h)	Cd ($\mu\text{ mol Cd per 100 g soil}$)							
		0.5	1	1.5	2	3	6	24	36
1		84.6	39.2	45.0	52.0	63.5	63.8	64.0	63.8
4		45.9	58.3	60.6	71.3	84.9	85.3	84.9	85.6
8		64.3	71.6	82.4	96.0	116.3	119.0	117.0	116.6

Studies on cumulative desorption to CaCl_2 showed that with sample nos. 4 and 8, 30–49% of adsorbed Cd can be desorbed from the soil, while >85% from soil no. 1. The amounts of Cd desorbed by CaCl_2 , MnCl_2 , CuCl_2 , ZnCl_2 or PbCl_2 from adsorbed soils are recorded in Table 4. The amount of Cd desorbed by the different cations follows the order, $\text{Pb} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cu} > \text{Mn} > \text{Ca}$ and

Fig. 2. Dependence of distribution coefficient of Cd between the solid and solution phases (K_d) on surface density of Cd (Γ) for the soils: (●) 1, (×) 4, and (○) 8.

desorption for the samples follows order $1 > 8 > 4$ which can be correlated with pH of the soil.

The results infer that as Cd uptake by plants is determined largely by its concentration in the soil solution, the observations provide some explanation for the greater uptake of Cd in acidic soils than in neutral or alkaline soils^{1,2-14}.

TABLE 4—DESORPTION OF Cd FROM SOILS (CONTAINING DIFFERENT AMOUNT OF Cd) TO CaCl_2 AND HEAVY METAL CHLORIDES

Concn of metal chloride $\mu\text{ mol ml}^{-1}$	Cd desorbed					
	Soil 1		Soil 4		Soil 8	
	$\mu\text{ mol Cd per 100 g soil}$	Adsorbed Cd %	$\mu\text{ mol Cd per 100 g soil}$	Adsorbed Cd %	$\mu\text{ mol Cd per 100 g soil}$	Adsorbed Cd %
125 CaCl_2	15.4	24.6	14.0	16.4	19.2	16.3
500 CaCl_2	38.9	60.8	23.0	27.0	53.0	44.9
125 CuCl_2	20.4	31.9	15.0	18.7	21.6	18.3
500 CuCl_2	46.2	72.2	26.4	30.8	56.9	48.2
125 MnCl_2	16.0	25.0	15.4	18.0	20.8	17.6
500 MnCl_2	31.0	41.5	25.3	30.0	55.0	46.7
125 ZnCl_2	18.8	29.4	16.9	19.7	22.2	18.8
500 ZnCl_2	48.3	75.3	28.2	32.9	58.6	49.6
125 PbCl_2	21.6	33.7	18.5	21.6	24.6	20.8
500 PbCl_2	51.2	80.0	30.0	35.0	61.4	52.0

References

1. A. L. PAGE, F. T. BINGHAM and C. NELSON, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1972, 1, 288.
2. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1968.
3. D. L. CARTER, M. D. HEILMAN and C. L. GONZALEZ, *Soil Sci.*, 1965, 100, 356.
4. H. J. M. BOWEN, "Trace Elements in Biochemistry", Academic, London, 1966.
5. M. FLRISCHER, A. F. SARAFIN, D. W. FASETT, P. HAMMOND, H. T. SCHACKLETT, I. C. T. NISBET and S. EPSTEIN, "Environmental Impact of Cadmium", 1974, Issue no. 7, pp. 263-323.
6. C. H. GILES, T. H. MAC EVAN, S. N. NAKHWA and D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3973.
7. H. VANDIRK, "Soil Biochemistry", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1971.
8. K. BUNZL, W. SCHMIDT and B. SANSONI, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1976, 27, 32.
9. R. RIFFALDI and R. LEVI-MENZI, *Water Air Soil Pollution*, 1975, 5, 179.
10. H. FARRAH and W. F. PICKERING, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1977, 30, 1417.
11. J. GARCIA-MIRAGAYA and A. L. PAGE, *Water Air Soil Pollution*, 1978, 9, 289.
12. S. C. JARVIS and L. H. P. JONES, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1980, 31, 469.
13. A. J. MACLEAN, *Can. J. Soil Sci.*, 1976, 56, 29.
14. A. ANDERSSON and K. O. NILSSON, *Ambio*, 1974, 3, 198.